

White paper

EU sustainability regulation: industry perspective

Tuomas Puttonen, Shunyang Ning, Roy Björkstrand, Mika Salmi

A!

Abstract

The European Union has been a forerunner in implementing sustainability policies and regulation in line with UN-led global sustainability treaties, such as the Paris Agreement. Becoming carbon neutral by 2050 and reducing greenhouse gas emissions -55% by 2030 are legally binding targets in EU environmental law. They offer a solid strategical foundation on top of which companies can plan their sustainability activities.

The existing objectives in environmental law are clear. However, same cannot be said of the legislative work of EU. In February 2025, the EU commission communicated a new proposal aiming to drastically simplify already accepted sustainability legislation. The fluctuating decision-making and the complicated legislation landscape can make it difficult for companies, especially SMEs with limited resources, to commit to sustainability actions and develop the required expertise.

This public document collects information, resources, and a timeline of major EU sustainability legislation (as of 2025 May) in one place. It also discusses the company actions and strategical implications reaching these targets would mean in the near and mid-term future.

Version 1.0.0 (13.5.2025)

Acknowledgements

The document has been prepared as part of a Business Finland co-research project 'Data-driven design for sustainability' (6292/31/2023) led by Aalto University. Improvement ideas, comments, or any factual errors can be reported to the corresponding author. Email address is discoverable at the Aalto University researcher portal.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	1
1.1. EU – the early mover in sustainability	3
1.2. Global greenhouse gas emissions	4
1.3. Environmental impacts and actions in Finland	5
2. Company sustainability requirements and strategies	8
2.1. Near and mid-term future (2025-2035).....	8
2.2. Mid- and long-term future (2035-2050)	11
2.3. From voluntary to mandatory sustainability reporting	12
2.4. Reporting greenhouse gas emissions.....	13
2.5. Data collection	14
3. Global and EU sustainability regulation	16
3.1. Global environmental treaties	16
3.2. EU Green Deal: from action plans to legislation	18
3.3. ‘Omnibus’ proposals: simplification of sustainability regulation?	19
3.4. EU financial regulation	22
3.4.1. EU Taxonomy Regulation	23
3.4.2. Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence (CSDDD)	25
3.4.3. Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)	26
3.5. EU industrial regulation	29
3.5.1. Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)	29
3.5.2. EU Emission Trading System (ETS)	31
3.6. EU product-level regulation	32
3.6.1. Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)	32
3.6.2. Right to repair	34
3.7. Future sustainability regulation	36
4. Sustainability assessment and communication	39
4.1. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	39
4.2. Environmental Product Declaration (EPD).....	46

1. Introduction

The hole in the ozone layer above Antarctica, identified by scientists by chance in 1985, quickly mobilized the whole World to phase out and ban ozone-depleting substances with the Montreal Protocol in 1987. The intervention was successful, and the ozone layer is expected to fully recover by 2060s. This ongoing success story proves the World can act together, and fast, when faced with global environmental crises.

However, now our planet Earth is not facing just one, but multiple environmental crises at the same time.

The World Economic Forum publishes an annual global risks report. In the survey results, environmental risks dominate the long-term (10-years forward) charts¹. If threats such as global warming, loss of biodiversity, increasing air pollution, and microplastic are left unchecked, it could, at worst, lead to an ecosystem collapse with serious consequences for the environment, humanity, and World economy.

Mitigating these threats and their adverse effects, requires a fundamental transition in the whole economic system, a green transition. Countries, companies, and individuals are forced to rethink their operations to sustain life on Earth – not just for us but also for future generations.

The global Paris Agreement² (with a goal to limit global warming to less than +1.5 °C) is the driving force for policies attempting to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The situation is assessed every five years. Paris Agreement works in a way that each country, or an entity (such as EU), will deliver, update, and act on their ‘nationally determined contributions’ (NDCs). These action plans provide an overview of national policies to reach net-zero emissions³.

The reaction of the European Union to the Paris Agreement and the ongoing climate crisis is known as the Green Deal. Under its umbrella, EU has approved various policy tools to curb global warming. For example, the Emission Trading System (ETS) places a price for each ton of emitted greenhouse gas (CO₂eq), the effort-sharing regulation (ESR) sets country-specific

¹ World Economic Forum. 2024. [Global Risks Report 2024: 19th Edition](#). Accessed: 9.5.2025

² United Nations. [Key aspects of the Paris Agreement](#). Accessed: 13.2.2025.

³ Climate Watch. 2024. [Net-Zero Tracker](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

reduction targets falling outside of the ETS system, and the EU Taxonomy steers financial markets and funding towards more sustainable operations.

However, the current policies have not been effective enough. As shown in **Figure 1**, the median global warming estimated by 2100 is nearly three degrees (+2.7 °C) ⁴. By early 2025, countries will deliver their next nationally determined contributions to the Paris Agreement⁵. With active policies, even limiting global warming to less than +2.0 °C seems unlikely. Thus, the ambition level will increase, promote new policies, and quicken the pace of existing regulation.

The sustainability regulation landscape is complex and constantly evolving. It can be hard for, especially small and medium-sized (SME), enterprises to follow the progress, acquire new competences, and comply with the requirements. The goal of this document is to present an overview of the major (2025) sustainability regulation for companies, its practical implications for companies, and how sustainability regulation is expected to develop in the future.

Figure 1. Global warming estimates for the year 2100. The 2022 situation (+1.2 °C), Paris Agreement goal (+1.5 °C), and projection with currently active policies (+2.7 °C). Original data by Climate Action Tracker adapted by Council on Foreign Relations.

A change is always a business opportunity. The fossil fuel era will end and make room for something new.

⁴ Climate Action Tracker. 2023. [The CAT Thermometer](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

⁵ World Resources Institute. 2024. [Next-generation Climate Targets: A 5-Point Plan for NDCs](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

Sustainability

The Brundtland Report⁶ in 1987 defined sustainable development as:

“Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

The same year, Earth was saved from its first environmental crisis when the Montreal Protocol led to an international agreement to phase out substances found responsible for the depletion of the ozone layer.

1.1. EU – the early mover in sustainability

The European union, with its Green Deal program, is a strong advocate of sustainability policies. This is not only a moral decision to fulfill the Paris Agreement obligations, but also a development program to position European countries and companies as forerunners in sustainable energy, products, and services.

On paper, the situation is favorable. In the 2023 data on primary energy⁷, the EU region stands out with higher-than-average shares of renewables in primary energy consumption. The diminishing role of fossil fuels and increasing electrification is especially evident for the Nordic countries. All countries which generate more than 40% of their primary energy from nuclear power are also situated in Europe.

With the tightening regulation, EU wants to become a technological leader for the post-fossil fuel era where hydrogen could become the green energy carrier. The ugly fact is that until very recently, EU economies have been running up to 60% on imported energy, of which roughly a fourth has been fossil fuels sourced from Russia. The Russia sanctions due to the invasion of Ukraine have also hit the EU economy hard and, on their part, accelerated the energy reform. Indeed, one goal of the EU decarbonization is to overcome such immobilizing energy-dependencies.

⁶ Brundtland Commission (organization independent of the UN created 1983 and dissolved in 1987 after releasing), 1987, “Our Common Future” report (ie. The Brundtland Report)

⁷ Our World in Data. 2024. [Global direct primary energy consumption. Share of primary energy consumption from renewables / fossil fuels / nuclear](#). Accessed: 4.2.2025.

1.2. Global greenhouse gas emissions

The global greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) 2023 are estimated 53.82 billion tonnes CO₂-equivalent⁸ (10¹² kg CO₂eq). As of 2025, the European Union is the fourth largest global emitter after China, United States, and India. In contrast, the emissions of Finland were approximately one per mille (0.1%) of the global emissions at 52.84 million tonnes⁹ (10⁹ kg CO₂eq). However, when looking at emissions per capita, an average Finnish person emits 14.1 tonnes of CO₂eq, considerably more than, for example, an average Chinese person at 9.8 tonnes CO₂eq.

Figure 2. Flow of global greenhouse gas emissions in 2021. Source: Climate Watch, based on raw data from IEA (2022), GHG Emissions from Fuel Combustion; modified by WRI.

Emissions by sectors

The Climate Watch and World Resources Institute interactive infographic (2021 data) provides an excellent overview how global greenhouse gas emissions are divided amongst sectors and industries¹⁰. A static version of the flow chart is shown in **Figure 2**. Majority of GHG stem from the energy sector (75.7%) followed by agriculture (11.7%), industrial processes (6.5%), waste (3.4%), and land use change and forestry (2.7%).

⁸ Our World in Data. 2023. [Greenhouse gas emissions](#). Accessed: 11.2.2025

⁹ Suomen virallinen tilasto (SVT): Kasvihuonekaasut [verkkojulkaisu]. ISSN=1797-6049. Helsinki: Tilastokeskus. [Accessed: 11.2.2025]. Available: <https://stat.fi/tilasto/khki>

¹⁰ Mengpin Ge, Johannes Friedrich and Leandro Vigna. 2024. [Where Do Emissions Come From? 4 Charts Explain Greenhouse Gas Emissions by Sector](#). Accessed: 11.2.2025.

The EU-specific data is available from the European Environment Agency, but has not been visualized with such rigor. Noteworthy is that in the 2022 EU data, the ‘industry’- category is seen to account for 20.3% of emissions.

Emission reduction and the Paris Agreement target

The EU average emissions have been declining steadily since 1990¹¹. In Finland, the decreasing trend started in the early 2000s. The global emissions however, except for a slight covid-19 drop, have continued climbing and are expected to plateau only by mid 2020s.

Current environmental policies have not been enough. The supporting research work and the first five-year assessment of the Paris Agreement progress, also called the first **Global Stocktake**¹², predicts a temperature increase between +2.5 – 2.9°C¹³. The assessment strongly urges countries to accelerate their sustainability actions and implement ambitious new policies to keep the +1.5°C target in reach. Countries and entities are expected to address the results of the first global stocktake and communicate their new plans in the updated Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) in 2025.

1.3. Environmental impacts and actions in Finland

Now let’s focus solely on the emissions and environmental impacts of Finland. **Figure 3** shows Statistics Finland data up to 2023 which is also reported as part of our responsibilities for the Paris Agreement in December 2024¹⁴. Noteworthy in the data is the LULUCF sector (land use, land-use change, and forestry), which has during the 2010s and 2020s transitioned from a clear carbon sink to a carbon source (black line).

¹¹ European Environment Agency. 2024. [Total net greenhouse gas emission trends and projections in Europe](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

¹² Jamal Srouji and Deirdre Cogan. World Resources Institute. 2023. [What Is the 'Global Stocktake' and How Can It Accelerate Climate Action?](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

¹³ UNEP. 2023. [Emission Gap Report 2023](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

¹⁴ Tilastokeskus. 2024. [Inventaarioraportointi Pariisin sopimukselle alkaa vuonna 2024](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

Figure 3. Greenhouse gas emissions of Finland with and without the LULUCF sector (land use, land-use change, and forestry). Statistics Finland.

Based on the Natural Resources Institute of Finland (Luke), the change in LULUCF is explained by increased loggings, increased CO₂ emissions from peatland forests, and emissions from croplands¹⁵.

It is estimated that Finland needs an additional carbon sink of 19 Mt CO₂ to reach the 2035 carbon neutrality goal. It is hard to see a future scenario where restrictions of loggings would not be required. In overall emissions, year 2023 is promising a change back to the decreasing trend. The preliminary data shows an 11% decrease in emissions mainly due to the changes in the energy sector (increase in nuclear and wind power)¹⁶.

Finland: Governmental climate planning

The Climate Law (10.6.2022/423)¹⁷ of Finland establishes a national climate policy planning system with a total of four recurring mandatory publications:

- Long term climate plan published minimum every 10 years
- Medium-term climate plan published each government term

¹⁵ Natural Resources Institute of Finland. 2023. [According to preliminary GHG inventory data, emissions from the land use sector increased in 2022](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

¹⁶ Tilastokeskus. 2024. [Sähköntuotantorakenteen muutos mahdollisti kasvihuonekaasupäästöjen tuntuvan laskun vuonna 2023](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

¹⁷ Finlex. [423/2022 Finnish Climate Law](#).

- Land use sector climate plan published every other government term
- Climate change mitigation plan published every other government term

These documents, to be accepted by the government, report on the status and success of existing climate policies in Finland and propose new policies to reduce emissions in the future. **The Annual Climate Report** by The Ministry of the Environment¹⁸ provides a broad overview of realized annual emissions and how it compares with reduction targets. It has become customary that each government term will publish **the National Climate and Energy Strategy**¹⁹, outlining measures to meet the EU climate commitments. In tandem with this publication, the Ministry of the Environment prepares a **Medium-term Climate Change Policy Plan**²⁰ which applies to the effort-sharing sector (sectors outside emission trading, except for the land use sector). These documents will both be updated in 2025. In addition, the first **Long-term Climate Strategy** is expected to be published.

The annual climate reports and national climate strategies provide indications how the Finnish (and EU) sustainability legislation is expected to develop in the short, mid, and long-term future.

Industry sector low-carbon roadmaps

Since 2020, The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment has coordinated voluntary **low-carbon roadmaps** where industry sectors have presented their current situation, evaluation of emission-reduction measures, and achievable reductions for the years 2030, 2035, and 2050²¹. In 2024, the industry roadmaps were published for the second time giving first indications how sectoral emission-reduction work is progressing. The more recent roadmaps, such as the one by Technology Industries of Finland, now includes an estimate of Scope 3 emissions²².

¹⁸ Ministry of the Environment. 2024. [Annual Climate Report 2024](#).

¹⁹ Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment. 2022. [Carbon neutral Finland 2035 – national climate and energy strategy](#).

²⁰ Ministry of the Environment. 2022. [Medium-term Climate Change Policy Plan: Towards a carbon-neutral society](#).

²¹ The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment. [Summary of Sectoral Low-Carbon Roadmaps 2024](#).

²² Vassinen, H., Järvinen, K. Auvinen, J., Aalto, L. Kallunki, J. Laine, A. Pokela, P. [Teknologiatoellisuuden vähähiilisyden tiekartta 2024](#).

2. Company sustainability requirements and strategies

The climate neutrality targets set in EU (and member state) environmental law provide (currently) the clearest mid and long-term strategical targets to reflect on business models, and their sustainability.

Carved in environmental law, EU is climate-neutral by 2050 and has reduced 55% of greenhouse gas emissions by 2030.

In addition, the EU commission has communicated a -90% target for 2040 which, with relatively high certainty, will be adopted as a new legally binding target.

2.1. Near and mid-term future (2025-2035)

In the short- and mid-term future (5-10 years), it is still rather straightforward for companies to reduce their emissions and reach the EU targets. The low-hanging fruits include actions such as a phase-out of fossil-derived products, transition to renewable energy, material recycling, and incremental improvements in product energy-efficiency.

The ‘big three’ of EU climate policies i) the national reduction targets of the *effort-sharing regulation*, ii) *emission trading system (ETS)*, and iii) *land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF)* regulations are doing much of the heavy lifting.²³ The EU emissions history and projections (1990-2050) are shown in **Figure 4a**. The projections, even with additional measures, ‘miss’ the 2030 -55% target with 6%. **Figure 4b** shows the individual targets and caps of the ‘big three’ -policies. Especially the effort-sharing targets are estimated to fall short on targets. For this reason, EU will be rolling out a second emission trading system (ETS II) which covers fuel combustion in buildings, road transport, and small industries²⁴, expected to be fully operational in 2027.

²³ European Environment Agency. 2024. [Total net greenhouse gas emission trends and projections in Europe](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025.

²⁴ EU Commission. [ETS II: buildings, road transport and additional sectors](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025.

a)

b)

Figure 4. a) EU greenhouse gas emission history, targets, and projections (1990-2050) and b) Historical emission, projections, and targets for the effort-sharing, emission trading system, and land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF) regulation

The first wave of company sustainability regulation will hit larger companies with the sustainability reporting directive (CSRD) already in place. The rollout of the corporate sustainability due diligence (CSDDD) directive is expected to bring more drastic effects for the whole value chain. In the directive, larger enterprises are required to assess their **whole global value chains** for human rights and sustainability. This will likely create a beneficial snowball effect as smaller suppliers are, even if not in the direct scope of the CSDDD, still obliged to provide information for the larger companies. The CSDDD will also state, for the first time in a written format, that company business models should be aligned with the Paris Agreement and EU sustainability targets. Target-setting and third-party verification for target alignment will become the norm with the work of the Science Based Targets Initiative²⁵ at the forefront. The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) will place a carbon-tax on imports outside of the EU region.

Apart from climate change policies, the EU work to halt biodiversity loss has advanced with the EU Nature Restoration Law in effect as of August 2024 despite Finland, amongst six other nations, voting against the initiative. Member States now have two years' time to develop their national restoration plans.²⁶ The first goal is to restore at least 20% of both land and sea areas by 2030. The nature restoration law and the LULUCF-regulation will affect the Finnish forestry industry and its yearly logging quotas.

Overview of current major regulation

- The already active EU Taxonomy regulation is a green classification and transparency system. It requires companies to assess the share of sustainable activities that fulfill a set of technical screening criteria and align with the EU sustainability goals
- The previous NFRD covered approximately 12000 companies. Once CSRD is fully operational it encompasses 50 000 large and listed SME companies in the EU region
- In CSRD, companies are required to extend the assessment of greenhouse gas emissions from Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions to Scope 3 emissions
- Many regulations such as the CSRD and CBAM impose a right for companies to request relevant supply chain data to fulfill their reporting obligations
- As an additional obligation, third-party validation becomes mandatory
- The Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), which will be transferred to EU member state legislation in 2026, requires large companies to

²⁵ Science Based Targets. 2024. [SBTi Corporate Net-Zero Standard Criteria](#). Version 1.2.

²⁶ EU Commission. 2024. [Degraded ecosystems to be restored across Europe as Nature Restoration Law enters into force](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025.

develop transition plans ensuring their business models are in alignment with the EU environmental law and the Paris Agreement 1.5°C targets

It is to be noted that, as of May 2025, the EU commission Omnibus simplification package is currently being processes and can have major impacts on the implementation and contents of existing and upcoming EU sustainability regulation (See Chapter 3.3 for details).

2.2. Mid- and long-term future (2035-2050)

But these actions can only take us so far. As seen in **Figure 4a**, towards the 2040 -90% and 2050 net-zero target, the challenge intensifies. The other environmental crises, for example, the biodiversity loss, deforestation, and accumulation of microplastics will require more attention. In the meanwhile, the world population continues to grow and will reach a maximum of ~10.3 billion people sometime in the 2080s.²⁷ Moving towards the carbon-neutrality targets 2050, the existing (effective) policies are expected to sustain with new additions introduced. Prediction is of course hard, yet initial hints of future policies can be deduced from EU communications and longer-term strategies. These in turn are often based on recommendations by different EU scientific advisory board(s). For example, the Climate Advisory Board has done a scenario analysis identifying the effectiveness, feasibility, and costs of different actions towards climate neutrality.²⁸

The EU Hydrogen Strategy is one of the cornerstones of the EU climate neutrality (and energy resilience) work moving forward. Hydrogen is seen as a viable energy carrier replacing fossil fuels.²⁹ However, according to the European Court of Auditors many of the communicated targets seem unrealistic both in terms of hydrogen production capacity and financing.³⁰

Full carbon neutrality by 2050 will also require deploying carbon removal, carbon storage and carbon-sequestering farming or forestry strategies – on a large scale. The recent Carbon

²⁷ United Nations. [World Population Prospects 2024](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

²⁸ European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change. 2023. [Scientific advice for the determination of an EU-wide 2040 climate target and a greenhouse gas budget for 2030–2050](#).

²⁹ EU Commission. 2020. A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe. [COM\(2020\) 301 final](#).

³⁰ European Court of Auditors. 2024. [The EU's industrial policy on renewable hydrogen Legal framework has been mostly adopted – time for a reality check](#).

Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) regulation creates the first voluntary framework to certify these activities.³¹

Finally, a more holistic change in the economy is created by transitioning to a **circular economy** as initially communicated via the Circular economy action plan.³² It allows for the current profit-driven capitalism to continue as usual, just in a different format.

Circular economy attempts to decouple economic growth and the use of natural resources.

Changing from a linear ‘take-make-waste’ model to a closed loop circular model, where natural resources and products are recycled, repaired, and reused, is of course a positive development for sustainability. Nevertheless, the criticism is targeted to the fact that it does not consider the root problem of most environmental issues, *overconsumption*.³³

Nevertheless, circular economy will be adopted, step-by-step, by EU to reach the more ambitious sustainability goals towards the 2040s and 2050s. The main piece of regulation, Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), is already in force as of July 2024. To give credit, the upcoming eco-design requirements will also indirectly reduce resource consumption because products have to be designed more durable, reusable, repairable, and energy efficient.³⁴ The concrete rules are, however, still pending.

2.3. From voluntary to mandatory sustainability reporting

In the past, ESG reporting has not been legally binding. This was changed only in 2016 by the EU non-financial reporting directive (NFRD), which was replaced by the corporate sustainability reporting directive (CSRD). Companies in the scope of the CSRD directive are required to submit their ESG data as part of the company annual reporting.

³¹ EU Commission. 2024. [Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025.

³² EU Commission. 2020. A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe. [COM\(2020\) 98 final](#).

³³ Mah, A., 2021. [Future-proofing capitalism: the paradox of the circular economy for plastics](#). Global Environmental Politics, 21(2), pp.121-142.

³⁴ EU Commission. 2024. [Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025.

ESG – environmental, social, and governance

The socially responsible investing gained momentum in the 70s and 80s and has been slowly evolving into the ESG (environmental, social, and governance) metrics of responsible investing that we know of today³⁵. The goal of these initiatives was not necessarily to improve the status of the environment, but to communicate investors on the capital risks caused by catastrophic environmental events such as oil spills. For reporting frameworks, such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) or the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), the reporting has been voluntary.

2.4. Reporting greenhouse gas emissions

Evaluating Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions is more straightforward as these emissions are directly controllable by the reporting company. Indirect, upstream and downstream Scope 3 emissions pose the real challenge. Depending on the focus area of the company, even up to 95-99% of the product lifecycle emissions may be Scope 3. This is especially true for companies which operate long-service life, energy-intensive machinery. High-quality reporting of these emissions requires collaboration, operations transparency, and data collection from both suppliers and customers. In the coming years, a failure for a supplier to comply with sustainability requirements can result in termination of the contract. It may become a real test of trust in the business relationship.

³⁵ Tom Krantz. IBM. 2024. [The history of ESG: A journey towards sustainable investing](#). Accessed: 13.2.2025.

Scope 1, 2, and 3 greenhouse gas emissions

Direct emissions originate from sources owned or controlled by a company

Indirect emissions are a consequence of company activities, but originate from sources owned or controlled by another company³⁶

To further avoid accounting same emissions multiple times, Greenhouse Gas Protocol (GHG) standards categorize emissions to three different ‘scopes’ according to their source in the value chain:

Scope 1 Direct emissions originating from the assets owned by the company, its energy production, and emissions from its machinery.

Scope 2 Indirect emissions to generate the energy purchased by the company.

Scope 3³⁷ Other indirect emission in the value chain.

The Greenhouse Gas Protocol has published a guidance document to help companies assess and calculate Scope 3 emissions of different categories.³⁸ They also maintain a comprehensive collection of life cycle database.³⁹

2.5. Data collection

Whether it is to assess greenhouse gas emissions or estimate a more detailed product- or company-level lifecycle assessment, everything comes down to quality data.

There are not yet established practices how required sustainability data should be acquired and how it would be shared efficiently amongst the parties. Even highly inefficient, single-use email queries and Excel sheets are not unheard of. Of course, a lot of the required data is already collected in various IT systems, such as the resource planning (ERP), product data (PDM & PLM), and sales systems. Unfortunately, these systems – even within companies – are often scattered. Access might be restricted to key personnel who might

Data for Scope 3 emissions and lifecycle assessment challenging as it requires cooperation and data interaction with suppliers and customers. A longer-term goal should be to establish data interfaces (API) and automate data collection within internal departments of a company as well as its external partners.

³⁶ Greenhouse Gas Protocol (GHG). [Corporate Accounting and Reporting Standard – Revised Edition](#).

³⁷ GHG. [Corporate Value Chain \(Scope 3\) Accounting and Reporting Standard](#).

³⁸ GHG. Technical Guidance for Calculating Scope 3 emissions (version 1.0).

³⁹ GHG. [Life Cycle Databases](#). Accessed: 4.2.2025.

Data collection is – and should be – an iterative process which is continuously evolving. Along the journey, data gaps should be identified and data quality progressively improved. The Greenhouse Gas Protocol Accounting and Reporting Standards provide the technical requirements and practical guidance on calculating emission but also on the data collection process.

It might be good practice to implement a few yearly company-internal and/or stakeholder projects where data quality is iteratively improved. In new product development, supplier agreements, and IT system development, planning on (sustainability) data collection and quality should be included in the normal process.

Supplier agreements: sustainability and data clauses

Companies who are subject to sustainability reporting and/or attempt to reach their carbon neutrality targets may have to start screening their supplier landscape to reach their targets. As mentioned, suppliers have a large impact on the Scope 3 emissions. In new agreements or revisions, suppliers may encounter a so-called sustainability clause in the supplier agreement. This means the buyer company is enforcing sustainability actions for the supplier. As a last resort, the company can reserve the right to terminate the contract if pre-defined sustainability criteria are not met.

3. Global and EU sustainability regulation

3.1. Global environmental treaties

Many of the international sustainability treaties can be traced back to the work of the United Nations (UN) and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) established already in 1972⁴⁰. One of the landmark international agreements of UNEP was the Montreal Protocol in 1987 to regulate and eventually phase out ozone-depleting substances, a few years after scientists had found a hole in the ozone layer above Antarctica⁴¹. UN has estimated that thanks to the Montreal Protocol actions, the ozone layer will largely have recovered by 2040⁴².

In 1988 UNEP, together with the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), established the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). The goal of the IPCC was, and still is, to prepare reviews of scientific information on climate change and provide recommendations for governmental climate policies⁴³. The reports have played an important role in the international climate change treaties that have followed, the first of which was the 1992 UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) recognising a global need to limit the “dangerous human interference with the climate system” and stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere.

The Kyoto Protocol In 1997 extended the original UNFCCC framework and was the first treaty to set legally binding targets to cut greenhouse gas emissions⁴⁴. It called for reducing the emissions of six greenhouse gases to 5.2 percent below the 1990 levels. However, the Kyoto Protocol only required 41 developed countries and the EU (out of 191 identified sovereign states as of 1997) to act and lacked the contribution of major polluters such as the United States, China, and India.

The current treaty in effect, the 2015 Paris Agreement, is destined to avoid these shortcomings and requires all countries to reduce greenhouse gases with a goal to limit the global average temperature rising over 1.5 °C compared to preindustrial levels⁴⁵.

The international work to address biodiversity loss is coordinated through the Convention of Biological Diversity signed by 196 UN parties. Compared to the climate change convention,

⁴⁰ UNEP. 2022. [50 years of Environmental Milestones](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

⁴¹ British Antarctic Survey. 2022. [The Ozone Hole](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

⁴² UN. 2023. [Ozone layer recovery is on track, due to success of Montreal Protocol](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

⁴³ Intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC). [History of the IPCC](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

⁴⁴ UN. 2022. [Marking the Kyoto Protocol's 25th anniversary](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

⁴⁵ UNFCCC. [Paris Agreement. What is the Paris Agreement?](#) Accessed: 12.5.2025

also originating from the same ‘Earth summit’ held in Rio Janeiro 1992, the work for biodiversity is lagging. The so-called Aichi Biodiversity Targets (2011 to 2020) failed miserably as not a single one of them was fully reached by 2020. It was only the 2022 COP15 Kunming-Montreal meeting chaired by China and organized in Canada that was able to put forward the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) with 23 targets, such as the catchy ‘30 by 30’ target aiming to protect 30 % of Earth land and ocean area and 30% of the degraded ecosystems by 2030⁴⁶. Many countries, Finland included, had promised – but did not deliver – a revised national action plan to the COP16 meeting held in Cali, Columbia⁴⁷.

The legally binding international treaties of the UNFCCC, such as the Paris Agreement, and informative climate reviews by the IPCC form the global backbone for environmental policymaking.

Figure 52. Overview of the global-to-local negotiation, decision-making, and legislative processes of environmental protection using climate change as an example.

⁴⁶ Convention on Biological Diversity. 2022. [COP15: Nations Adopt Four Goals, 23 Targets for 2030 In Landmark UN Biodiversity Agreement](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

⁴⁷ WWF. 2024. [Too few countries on track to restore nature by 2030, unveils new country tracker ahead of global nature conference](#). Accessed: 12.5.2025

3.2. EU Green Deal: from action plans to legislation

EU has set legally binding greenhouse gas reduction targets in environmental law. EU must be climate neutral by 2050 and reduce 55% of its greenhouse gas emissions by 2030. An additional goal of 90% emission reduction by 2040 has been proposed by the EU Commission.

As shown in **Figure 5**, the consensus reached in the global negotiation process of the United Nations will lead to global Agreements = Treaties = Protocols (such as the Paris Agreement) which, if ratified by enough UN members, take effect. It can be seen as a higher-level moral promise where countries agree on common goals and processes for a global challenge, in this case: climate change. Once the abstract goal is defined the implementation burden falls downwards to individual member states, or in our case, for the European Union. EU Green Deal is the EU overarching reaction to UN-identified environmental ‘triple planetary crisis’ (climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution). The objectives that eventually materialize as legally binding directives or regulations are first laid out as environmental strategies and action plans⁴⁸ under the *Green Deal*, such as the *Biodiversity Strategy*, *Circular Economy Action Plan*, or the *Zero Pollution Action Plan*.

Of the three planetary crises, climate change work is well underway, much owing to the international consensus formed based on scientific evidence and the Kyoto Protocol-to-Paris Agreement. Obligations to reduce greenhouse gases are now laid out as legally binding targets in EU environmental law, with the EU climate neutrality target set to year 2050 (EU Climate Law (2018/1999) amended by regulation 2021/1119⁴⁹) and a legally binding interim goal of 55% emission reduction set to year 2030. A recent EU Commission report provides an excellent overview of climate change mitigation actions.⁵⁰

Much of the reductions are achieved through the ETS systems, implemented already for the Kyoto Protocol, effort sharing regulation to cut non-ETS member state emissions, and increasing carbon sinks through the land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF) regulation. The objective of the European Union ‘Fit for 55’ legislative package in 2021 was to help realize the -55% interim goal with 13 revisions to existing legislation and 6 new proposals.

⁴⁸ EU Commission. [Environmental strategies and action plans](#). Accessed: 6.11.2024

⁴⁹ EU Lex. [Amendment to European Climate Law. 2021/1119](#).

⁵⁰ EU Commission. [EU Climate Action Progress Report 2024](#).

The EU work and legislation to halt and reverse biodiversity loss is laid out in the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030⁵¹, which covers all the targets agreed in the 15th conference of the Global Biodiversity Convention in Kunming-Montreal. Similarly, the Zero Pollution Action Plan⁵² collects policies and the EU vision how pollution levels in air, water, and soil can be reduced to levels no longer harmful for humans nor natural ecosystems. Compared with the work on climate change, these areas are lagging behind.

The European Climate Law and EU Commission Green Deal policy tools, some of which apply on the union level, and some implemented in national legislation, help the European Union and Member States fulfill their sustainability obligations.

3.3. ‘Omnibus’ proposals: simplification of sustainability regulation?

The EU sustainability regulation is, unfortunately, in a state of uncertainty. On 26th of February 2025, the EU commission communicated two proposals, so called ‘Omnibus’ packages, aiming to significantly simplify sustainability regulation⁵³. The proposals were justified with a goal to safeguard EU company competitiveness. EU Commission wants to relief companies, especially SMEs, on excessive reporting burden. **Figure 6** presents the modified regulation timeline if the proposals are fully adopted as legislation. The currently valid timeline is shown in **Figure 7**.

⁵¹ EU Commission. [Biodiversity strategy for 2030](#). Accessed: 6.2.2025

⁵² EU Commission. [Zero Pollution Action Plan](#). Accessed: 6.2.2025

⁵³ EU Commission. 2025. [Commission simplifies rules on sustainability and EU investments, delivering over €6 billion in administrative relief](#). Accessed: 2.4.2025.

Figure 63. EU sustainability regulation timeline 2023-2030 if all changes proposed by EU Commission Omnibus simplification packages take effect.

The following subchapters summarize the main changes of the Commission proposed Omnibus packages. It is to be noted that this is only a legislative initiative by the EU Commission which will still go through normal EU legislative procedure. In up to three readings the proposal is examined, can be rejected or modified, and must be accepted by both the EU Parliament and EU Council.

EU Commission ‘staff working documents’ (SWD), accompanying each Omnibus proposal, offer an excellent source of information detailing the proposed changes and explaining the underlying reasoning

EU Taxonomy regulation

The Omnibus package would affect EU Taxonomy regulation in two ways. The package proposes changes to CSRD taxonomy reporting. The second route is more direct with amendments to Taxonomy Disclosures, Climate, and Environmental Delegated Acts. The

feedback period for the draft acts has ended and commission adoption is planned for second quarter of 2025.⁵⁴

- In the proposal SMEs are excluded from mandatory reporting with obligations applied only to large companies with over 1000 employees and net turnover above 450 M€.
- Reduction of reporting data points by ~70%
- Industry feedback is collected to simplify the ‘do no significant harm’ criteria for pollution prevention

Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)

The proposed changes would significantly affect the scope, contents, and timeline of CSRD reporting.^{55 56 57} Companies in the scope of CSRD reporting would be reduced by nearly 80%.

- Reporting is proposed to be mandatory only for large undertakings with more than 1000 employees AND turnover above 50 M€ OR a balance sheet total of over 25 M€.
- ESRS standards will be revised with data points reduced and unclear rules clarified
- Sector-specific standards will no longer be developed
- A voluntary reporting standard will be developed for out-of-scope companies. This standard will also act as a ‘shield’ meaning that larger undertakings cannot request SMEs for value chain information (for their own CSRD reporting) if it is not included in the voluntary standard
- Moving to reasonable assurance from limited assurance would no longer be required
- Postponing reporting requirements for CSRD ‘waves’ 2 and 3 by two years

⁵⁴ EU Commission. [Taxonomy Delegated Acts – amendments to make reporting simpler and more cost-effective for companies](#). Accessed: 3.4.2025.

⁵⁵ EU Commission. [Proposal for a Directive amending the Audit Directive, Accounting Directive, Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive, and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive - Omnibus I - COM\(2025\)81](#). Accessed: 3.4.2025.

⁵⁶ EU Commission. [Proposal postponing the application of some reporting requirements in the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive and the transposition deadline and application of the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive - Omnibus I - COM\(2025\)80](#). Accessed: 3.4.2025.

⁵⁷ EU Commission. SWD(2025) 80. [Staff working document accompanying COM\(2025\)80 and COM\(2025\)81](#). Accessed: 3.4.2025.

Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)

The Omnibus package proposes to significantly change scope and content of CBAM regulation.^{58 59} In the proposal, an estimated 90% of current in-scope companies would no longer be required to report (and pay). Commission estimates that, despite the change, 99% of CO2 emission would still be covered. Further proposals are planned for early 2026 to address risks of carbon leakage.

- Individuals and SMEs are no longer in scope of the CBAM regulation
- Small and occasional companies, importing less than a 50-ton per year threshold, would no longer be in scope of the CBAM
- For remaining companies in scope, the package proposes simplifications for authorization of declarants, emission calculation, reporting requirements, and financial liability compliance

Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD)

EU Commission proposes significant changes to the CSDDD timeline, scope of the impacted value chain, and limiting information CSDDD in-scope companies may request from SME and small midcap companies.

- The implementation of CSDDD is postponed by one year
- The due diligence process does not cover the whole value chain but is only limited to direct, Tier 1, business partners
- Removing the obligation to terminate a business partnership as a last resort
- Member state legislation cannot deviate (be stricter) than EU legislation

3.4. EU financial regulation

The following chapters will present the major EU directives and regulation (in force) which are considered relevant in the context of machine building and technology industries of Finland. Many of the regulations will take effect in stages, rolling out first for larger companies. **Figure 7** presents a timeline of sustainability regulation and its phases of activation.

⁵⁸ EU Commission. [Proposal for amending Regulation \(EU\) 2023/956 as regards simplifying and strengthening the carbon border adjustment mechanism - Omnibus I - COM\(2025\) 87](#). Accessed: 3.4.2025.

⁵⁹ EU Commission. SWD(2025) 58. [Staff working document accompanying COM\(2025\) 87](#). Accessed: 3.4.2025.

Figure 74. EU sustainability regulation timeline 2023 – 2030. Main policies in effect and to be activated before the EU environmental law 55% reduction target of 2030.

3.4.1. EU Taxonomy Regulation

Background: The EU Taxonomy is a classification system established by the European Union to define which economic activities can be considered environmentally sustainable. It is part of the EU's broader efforts to meet its climate and environmental objectives, particularly the goal of making Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050.

What: EU Taxonomy is a classification system, that is an important market transparency tool that helps direct investments to activities most needed for the transition to net zero and environmental sustainability⁶⁰.

The Taxonomy sets out six environmental objectives: Climate Change mitigation, climate change adaptation, sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, transition to a circular economy, pollution prevention and control, and protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems.

Why: The main goal of the EU Taxonomy is to provide a clear and common understanding of what constitutes a sustainable investment, which helps guide investment towards

⁶⁰ European Commission. 2024. [EU Taxonomy's uptake on the ground](#). Accessed: 9.5.2025

environmentally sustainable projects. It serves as a tool for investors, companies, and policymakers to identify and support green investments.

Affected stakeholders: companies, banks & financial markets, public sector, and investors.

Practical implications for companies:

- Disclosure Obligations: Companies subject to the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD) are required to disclose specific information regarding their environmentally sustainable activities.
- Prepare for Disclosure: Develop systems to accurately track and report the proportion of your turnover, CapEx, and OpEx related to environmentally sustainable activities.
- Action Points for Companies: Companies not covered by the NFRD are not legally required to disclose under the EU Taxonomy. However, Companies under CSRD must disclose how their activities align with the EU Taxonomy.
- Upcoming Simplifications: The EU may reduce reporting burdens by a third, allowing more flexibility in data use and simplifying company obligations while maintaining sustainability goals.

Detailed requirements for the disclosure and reporting can be found in the EU publications.⁶¹

Timeline:

- March 2018: EU publishes the Action Plan on Financing Sustainable Growth.
- June - July 2020: Taxonomy Regulation adopted and published and enters into force.
- December 2021: Climate Delegated Act and Disclosure Rules (Article 8 DA) published.
- July 2022: Complementary Climate Delegated Act includes nuclear & gas under strict conditions.
- November 2023: Environmental Delegated Act expands to all six environmental objective

Developer: EFRAG authorized by EU commission

⁶¹ European Union. 2021. [Commission Delegated Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2178](#).

3.4.2. Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence (CSDDD)

Background: The Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), officially known as Directive (EU) 2024/1760, is a significant legislative measure adopted by the European Union to promote sustainable and responsible corporate behavior throughout global value chains.

What: Companies are forced to identify, prevent, end, or mitigate their harmful impacts to human rights and the environment, including their whole value chains. Certain large companies are required to report a plan to comply with the 1,5 °C global warming limit of the Paris Agreement.

Companies are required to integrate their sustainability disclosures directly into the management report section of their annual financial reports ⁶²

Affected stakeholders: Eventually EU companies and parent companies with over 1000 employees and turnover exceeding 450 M€, EU companies with franchising agreements having a worldwide turnover more than 80 M€ if at least 22,5 M€ in royalties, and non-EU companies operating within EU and exceed the beforementioned criteria. However, the reporting will have to cover the whole value chain.

Practical implications for companies:

- Due Diligence Policy Disclosure: Companies are required to publicly disclose their due diligence policies, detailing the processes implemented to identify, prevent, mitigate, and account for actual and potential adverse impacts.
- Annual Reporting: Companies must include a description of their due diligence processes and their outcomes in their annual reports.
- Transition Plan for Climate Change Mitigation: Large companies are obligated to adopt and implement a transition plan for climate change mitigation, aligned with the 2050 climate neutrality objective of the Paris Agreement.
- Enforcement and Penalties: Member States are responsible for enforcing the directive through designated national authorities, which have the power to impose sanctions, including fines, for non-compliance.

Timeline:

Phase I (2027-): Companies with over 5000 employees and worldwide turnover over 1500M€

Phase II (2028-): Companies with over 3000 employees and worldwide turnover over 900M€

⁶² Greenomy. 2024. [Sustainability Reporting: How is a CSRD Report Structured?](#) Accessed: 9.5.2025

Phase III (2029-): All remaining companies listed as affected stakeholders

EU directive: CSDDD 2024/1760 entered in force 25th of July 2024⁶³

Finnish law: Member States must transpose the Directive into national law and communicate the relevant texts to the Commission within two years, by 26th of July 2026⁶⁴.

3.4.3. Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)

Background: Since 2014, listed companies with more than 500 employees have been required to report their social and environmental impacts in accordance with the non-financial reporting directive (NFRD). The corporate sustainability reporting directive (CSRD) replaces and updates the NFRD legislation. In addition, the reporting responsibilities will be extended to small and medium-sized enterprises and are expected to increase the reporting coverage from 11700 to about 50000 companies in the EU region.

What: Annual reporting of company social and environmental impacts, according to the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), mandatory reporting for the year 2024 for large and listed enterprises and gradually towards 2028 for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Why: For sustainability transparency, development of responsible business models, and standardization of reporting practices. The reporting standardization has been discussed with International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) and Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) to minimize any double reporting.

Affected stakeholders: Large EU companies, gradually medium-sized and small EU companies, and large non-EU companies

Practical implications for companies:

- Expanded Reporting Requirements: companies must disclose detailed information on how sustainability issues affect their business and the impact of their activities on people and the environment.
- Adherence to European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS): The CSRD mandates the use of ESRS, developed by the European Financial Reporting Advisory

⁶³ European Union. 2024. [Directive \(EU\) 2024/1760. Corporate sustainability due diligence](#). Accessed: 9.5.2025

⁶⁴ Työ- ja elinkeinoministeriö. 2024. [Direktiivi yritystoiminnan kestävästä toimintaa koskevasta huolellisuusvelvoitteesta](#) (Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive, CSDDD). Accessed 9.5.2025

Group (EFRAG), ensuring standardized and comparable sustainability information across the EU.

- Verification requirements: Reported sustainability information must undergo limited assurance by an independent auditor or certifier, enhancing the reliability of the disclosed data.
- Digital Reporting: Companies are required to prepare their sustainability reports in a digital, machine-readable format and tag them according to a digital taxonomy.

Timeline:

Phase 1 (2024–): all large companies which were already covered by NFRD and meet at least two of the three requirements:

- 500 or more employees
- 40 M€ net turnover
- 20 M€ in assets

Phase II (2025 –): all large companies and the previously mentioned requirements

- More than 250 employees
- Net turnover exceeding €50 million
- Balance sheet total over €43 million

Phase III (2026 –): Small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) listed on EU-regulated markets that meet at least two of the three requirements:

- More than 10 employees
- More than 700 k€ net revenue
- More than 350 k€ in assets

Phase IV (2028–): All non-EU companies with net turnover above 150 M€ in the EU and if they have at least one subsidiary or branch in the EU

EU directive: CSRD 2022/2464⁶⁵, entered in force 5th of January 2023

⁶⁵ European Union. 2022. Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 537/2014, Directive 2004/109/EC, Directive 2006/43/EC and Directive 2013/34/EU, as regards corporate sustainability reporting. Official Journal of the European Union, L 322, pp. 15–80, 16 December. Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2464/oj>

Finnish law: Changes were made to the Accounting Law 1336/1997, Auditing Act 1141/2015, and their dependencies, which were accepted by the Finnish parliament 21st of December 2023⁶⁶

Related regulation: EU Taxonomy 2020/852, ESRS C(2023)5303, SFDR 2019/2088

European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS)

What: The European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) provide companies with detailed reporting contents and structure to comply with the CSRD directive. The twelve (ESRS 1-12) industry sector-agnostic standards are organized under *cross-cutting, environmental, social, and governance* categories. The full standards are available as Annexes to the EU Commission delegated regulation 2023/2772 published 31st of July 2023⁶⁷.

Why: Sustainability transparency, comparability between reporting data, alignment between previous global standards such as GRI (Global Reporting Initiative)

Affected stakeholders: Companies required to report according to CSRD. However, non-CSRD companies in the value chain have an obligation to provide information.

Timeline: First ESRS set provides sector-agnostic standards. Sector-specific standards are in different phases of development by EFRAG⁶⁸, as authorized by EU commission.

EU Law: The first set of ESRS reporting standards for the CSRD were adopted via a EU Commission delegated regulation 2023/2772 on 31st of July 2023⁶⁹

Finnish law: The provisions related to the CSRD entered into force on the 31st of December 2023.

⁶⁶ Valtioneuvosto. 2022. Hallituksen esitys: Yritysten kestävyysraportointi (CSRD-direktiivi), TEM082:00/2022. Available at: <https://valtioneuvosto.fi/hanke?tunnus=TEM082:00/2022>

⁶⁷ European Union. 2023. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772 of 31 July 2023 supplementing Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards sustainability reporting standards. Official Journal of the European Union, L 2023/2772, 22 December. Available at: http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2023/2772/oj

⁶⁸ EFRAG. Sector specific ESRS. Available: <https://www.efrag.org/en/sustainability-reporting/esrs-workstreams/sectorspecific-esrs>, Accessed: 27.8.2024

⁶⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32023R2772>

3.5. EU industrial regulation

3.5.1. Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)

Background: CBAM was introduced as part of the EU's Green Deal to prevent carbon leakage by aligning carbon costs of imports with EU standards.

What: an EU policy aimed at leveling the playing field for carbon-intensive goods by ensuring that imported products pay the same carbon price as those produced within the EU. This mechanism helps prevent carbon leakage—where companies might move production to countries with laxer climate policies—and encourages global industries to adopt cleaner production methods.

Involved goods: Iron and Steels, iron ore, certain fertilizers, aluminum, cement, chemicals and electricity.

Why: It aligns with the phase-out of free allowances under the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) to support the decarbonization of European industry while remaining compatible with World Trade Organization (WTO) rules. It directly affects the cost structure of importing carbon-intensive goods into the EU.

Affected stakeholders: Companies in EU, non –EU exporters of carbon intensive goods

Practical implications for companies:

- **CBAM Goods Covered:** CBAM applies to specific goods that are emissions-intensive and at risk of "carbon leakage." The currently covered sectors include: Cement, Iron and, Aluminium, Hydrogen, Fertilizers.
- **Reporting:** An importer of CBAM-regulated goods is required to submit quarterly reports detailing the quantity of imported goods, their embedded emissions, the carbon price paid in the country of origin, the production, and any additional sector-specific information.
- **Embedded Emissions Calculation:** Determine direct and indirect emissions . If supplier data is unavailable, use default values provided by the EU Commission.
- **Carbon Price Adjustments:** If a carbon price has been paid in the country of origin, the CBAM obligation may be reduced accordingly, but reports of evidence must be provided.
- **Compliance and Penalties:** Submitting accurate CBAM reports is mandatory. Failure to comply can result in penalties ranging from €10 to €50 per ton of unreported emissions.

More detailed information and regulation requirements can be found in the “Guidance Document on CBAM Implementation for Importers of Goods into the EU ⁷⁰” published by EU.

Timeline:

- **2023-2025:** Transitional phase where reporting obligations start, but no financial payments are required.
- **January 1, 2026:** Full implementation begins. Importers will start paying the carbon border adjustment fee.
- **Phase-out of Free Allowances:** Aligns with the gradual reduction of free allowances under the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS).

EU regulation: CBAM regulation 2023/956

Finnish law: 1288/2023 to implement the mechanism in Finland and 1289/2023 to extend the responsibilities of the Customs Agency of Finland as the implementing body (Both active as of 1.1.2024). Changes are proposed to the law which would take effect 1.1.2025⁷¹

⁷⁰ European Commission. (2023). Available: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/document/download/bc15e68d-566d-4419-88ec-b8f5c6823eb2_en?filename=Guidance+document+on+CBAM+implementation+for+importers+of+goods+into+the+EU.pdf

⁷¹ Työ- ja elinkeinoministeriö. 2024. EU:n hiilirajamekanismia (CBAM) koskeva lakiluonnos lausunnolle [Press release] 7 June. Available at: <https://tem.fi/-/eu-n-hiilirajamekanismia-cbam-koskeva-lakiluonnos-lausunnolle-1>

3.5.2. EU Emission Trading System (ETS)

Background: The emission trading system is a policy instrument that was first conceived to reach the legally binding greenhouse gas reduction targets set in the 1997 Kyoto protocol⁷². The EU ETS, adopted as a directive in 2003 and launched in 2005, was the first international emission trading system. Currently, the system is in its fourth phase lasting from 2021 until 2030 and covers 10,000 installations in the energy sector and manufacturing as well as aviation operators within EU. As of 2024, 36 ETS systems are in place globally, covering 58% of the global GDP and 18% of global emissions⁷³. Further 22 systems are in consideration.

What: The ETS is a 'cap and trade' system in which the overall greenhouse emissions are limited, or capped, to a certain level and traded within the market. The level of the cap determines how many allowance units, worth of 1 tonne of CO² equivalents (tCO²e), are available for EU companies to use. In the initial phases of the ETS system, free allowances were allocated to protect sectors with a risk of production shifting to countries outside of the EU (carbon leakage). The issuance of free allowances will gradually cease with the CBAM implementation.

Why: A policy instrument to control the overall amount of greenhouse gas emissions and encourage decarbonization within the EU region. In phase 4, the emission cap is decreasing linearly 2.2 % every year.

Affected stakeholders: The Producers of energy (≥ 20 MW), oil refineries, coke ovens, iron and steel, cement clinker, glass, lime, bricks, ceramics, pulp, paper and board, aviation, aluminum, petrochemicals, ammonia, production of certain acids, CO₂ capture, CO₂ transport and geo-storage.

Timeline:

- Phase 1 (2005-2007): Served as a pilot phase to establish a carbon pricing mechanism and develop the necessary infrastructure for monitoring, reporting, and verification.
- Phase 2 (2008-2012): Aligned with the Kyoto Protocol's first commitment period, introducing stricter caps and expanding coverage to additional sectors and gases.

⁷² European Commission, Development of EU ETS (2005-2020), Available: https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets/development-eu-ets-2005-2020_en, Accessed 23.8.2024

⁷³ International Carbon Action Partnership. 2024. Emission Trading Worldwide: 2024 ICAP Status Report. Available: <https://icapcarbonaction.com/en/publications/emissions-trading-worldwide-2024-icap-status-report>, Accessed: 27.8.2024

- Phase 3 (2013-2020): Implemented significant reforms, including a centralized EU-wide cap, increased auctioning of allowances, and the introduction of the Market Stability Reserve to address surplus allowances.
- Phase 4 (2021-2030): Aims to further tighten the emissions cap, expand sectoral coverage, and align the system with the EU's enhanced climate targets under the European Green Deal.

EU directive: Directive 2003/87/EC⁷⁴. The authority to revise the system is on the EU level and only the EU commission can alter it.

Finnish law: Law on emission trading 1270/2023⁷⁵

3.6. EU product-level regulation

3.6.1. Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)

What: The ESPR replaces the Ecodesign directive 2009/125/EC. The ESPR regulation is a framework legislation, which means that concrete 'ecodesign requirements' will be progressively decided on a product-by-product basis.

- Introduces a digital product passport (DPP) which is destined to improve transparency of product materials, their origins, and product lifecycle environmental impacts.
- Bans the destruction of unsold textiles and footwear
- Requires public authorities to follow green procurement criteria

Why: The ecodesign directive and upcoming ESPR regulation ensure longer-lasting, resource-efficient products, which are easier to repair, and recycle. The regulation is also expected to improve product information transparency so that all stakeholders can better assess product sustainability.

Affected stakeholders: Original equipment manufacturers. The rules will apply to ALL products placed on the EU market, regardless of where they have been originally produced.

⁷⁴ European Union. 2003. Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC. Official Journal of the European Union, L 275, pp. 32–46, 25 October. Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2003/87/oj>

⁷⁵ Finland. 2023. Laki päästökaupasta 1270/2023 [Emissions Trading Act]. Announced 28 December. Finlex. Available at: <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/lainsaadanto/2023/1270>

Practical implications for companies:

- **Product Design:** Ensure products are durable, repairable, energy-efficient, and recyclable.
- **Digital Product Passports (DPPs):** Implement DPPs to provide essential product information, enhancing transparency and compliance.
- **Supply Chain Management:** Identify and manage hazardous substances; collaborate with suppliers to meet ESPR standards.
- **End-of-Life Management:** Establish take-back programs and strategies to minimize production and post-use waste.
- **Compliance and Reporting:** Stay updated on ESPR requirements; maintain records demonstrating compliance.
- **Market Opportunities:** Use ESPR as a chance to innovate and gain a competitive edge in sustainability.

Timeline: The work to implement the regulation has started with stakeholder consultations. Commission is required to publish the first ESPR working plan in the first half of 2025⁷⁶. There will be a transition period where both instruments apply. The current Ecodesign and Energy Labelling Working Plan 2022-2024⁷⁷ is still active.

EU regulation: Ecodesign for Sustainable Products 2024/1781⁷⁸ in force as of 18th of July 2024.

Finnish law: Law on Ecodesign 1009/2010

⁷⁶ European Commission. 2024. Implementing the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (https://green-forum.ec.europa.eu/implementing-ecodesign-sustainable-products-regulation_en).

⁷⁷ Directorate-General for Energy. 2022. Ecodesign and Energy Labelling Working Plan 2022–2024. Brussels: European Commission. Available at: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/publications/ecodesign-and-energy-labelling-working-plan-2022-2024_en

⁷⁸ European Union. 2024. Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for sustainable products, amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and repealing Directive 2009/125/EC. Official Journal of the European Union, L 2024/1781, 28 June. Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1781/oj>

3.6.2. Right to repair

Background: In EU region, the premature disposal of goods causes an estimated 261 million tons of CO₂-equivalent emissions each year⁷⁹. The trend of short-lived products and planned obsolescence is especially embodied in the smartphone market. For example, the operation of replacing a battery has been made impossible to a normal consumer by claims of voiding warranty or impossibility to disassemble products.

What: The ‘Right to repair’ directive places an obligation for certain product manufacturers to repair products within a reasonable time and cost. It also prohibits manufacturers from preventing second-hand repair with either contractual clauses, hardware, or software. After repair, the legal product guarantee is extended for a full year. In addition, manufacturers are required to transparently provide information about repair services and spare part costs.

Why: Extend the lifetime of products, reduce emissions linked with premature disposal of consumer goods, promote a circular economy, and revitalize the EU repair market.

Affected stakeholders: Producers of consumer products. Currently affected product categories are listed in the Annex II of the Directive.

Practical implications for companies:

- **Mandatory Repairs Post-Warranty:** Manufacturers must offer repair services for products beyond the legal guarantee period, ensuring repairs are provided at a reasonable price and within a reasonable timeframe.
- **Access to Spare Parts and Repair Information:** Companies are required to provide consumers and independent repairers with access to spare parts, tools, and repair information, facilitating easier and more cost-effective repairs.
- **Incentives for Repair:** The directive encourages the use of repair vouchers and funds to make repairs more appealing to consumers, promoting a culture of repair over replacement.
- **Online Repair Platforms:** An online platform will be established to help consumers find local repair services and shops selling refurbished goods, increasing the visibility and accessibility of repair options.

⁷⁹ European Parliament. 2024. Right to repair: Making repair easier and more appealing to consumers. [press release] 23 April. Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240419IPR20590/right-to-repair-making-repair-easier-and-more-appealing-to-consumers>

Timeline:

- Affected products in Annex II will be annually updated
- Online platform to find repairers expected to be operational in 2027

EU directive: ‘Right to repair’ 2024/1799⁸⁰ entered in force 30th of July 2024.

Finnish law: Member States must transpose the Directive into national law and communicate the relevant texts to the Commission within two years, by 31st of July 2026.

Related regulation: Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Directive EU/2024/825 on Empowering Consumers in the Green Transition.

⁸⁰ European Union. 2024. Directive (EU) 2024/1799 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on common rules promoting the repair of goods and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directives (EU) 2019/771 and (EU) 2020/1828. Official Journal of the European Union, L 2024/1799, 10 July. Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/1799/oj>

3.7. Future sustainability regulation

In the upcoming years, the focus will be on tightening environmental regulations, increasing investments in clean technologies, and reforming key sectors like transportation and energy. The Fit for 55 package will play a crucial role in this, aiming for a 55% reduction in net greenhouse gas emissions by 2030⁸¹. Moreover, the EU is preparing to implement a new climate target for 2040, aiming for a 90% reduction in net greenhouse gas emissions relative to 1990 levels. The approach includes revisions in emissions trading systems, support for renewable energy, and stricter efficiency standards across industries, reinforcing Europe's leadership in combating climate change.

EU circular economy action plan

The EU is set to introduce a suite of legislative measures that will reshape industries by embedding circular economy principles deeply into product lifecycles and production processes. Under the Circular Economy Action Plan, sectors such as electronics, textiles, packaging, and construction will face tighter eco-design standards and extended producer responsibility requirements—mandating that products be designed for durability, repairability, and recyclability, while also streamlining waste management practices to keep materials in continuous circulation.

For example, the Commission proposed revising the Waste Framework Directive to hold textile producers accountable for the entire lifecycle of their products, promoting sustainable textile waste management, while also setting targets to reduce food waste by 10% in processing and manufacturing and by 30% per capita in retail, restaurants, food services, and households by 2030 compared to 2020 levels⁸².

EU Emission Trading System II (ETS II)

As part of the 2023 revisions of the ETS Directive, a new emissions trading system named ETS2 was created, separate from the existing EU ETS. This new system will cover and

⁸¹ European Commission. 2024. Fit for 55: delivering the European Green Deal

https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/delivering-european-green-deal/fit-55-delivering-proposals_en.

⁸² European Parliament. 2025. New Circular Economy Action Plan – Legislative Train 04.2025. Brussels: European Parliament. Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-new-circular-economy-action-plan>

address the CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion in buildings, road transport and additional sectors (mainly small industries not covered by the existing EU ETS). The carbon price set by the ETS2 will provide a market incentive for investments in building renovations and low-emissions mobility.

ETS2 operates as a cap-and-trade system, but with a key difference compared to the existing EU ETS: it covers emissions upstream. This means that fuel supplier will be required to monitor, report, and ultimately surrender allowances to cover their emissions. The overall cap is designed to reduce emissions by 42% by 2030 compared to 2005 levels.

Phased Implementation:

- **2025:** Monitoring and reporting of emissions will commence.
- **2027:** fully operational. During 2027, the system will auction 30% more allowances than initially planned to enhance market liquidity.

*Potential Delay: If there are exceptionally high gas or oil prices in 2026, implementation could be postponed until 2028 to ensure a smooth transition.

ETS2 includes a **Market Stability Reserve** to regulate allowance prices, releasing extra allowances if they exceed €45 (adjusted to 2020) in the first three years or rise rapidly. **Permit Requirement** mandates all regulated entities to obtain a greenhouse gas permit by 1 January 2025 and implement an approved emissions monitoring plan. **Annual Reporting** requires entities to submit emissions reports by 30 April each year, with verification by an accredited verifier starting in 2026. From 2028, **Allowance Surrender** obliges entities to surrender allowances by 31 May based on their verified emissions.

EU Green claims

Today, many product information and marketing claims are vague, misleading or unfounded. EU green claims initiative is designed to tackle misleading green washing claims. It aims to create a level playing field by ensuring that all environmental claims are based on reliable, verifiable evidence.⁸³

For businesses, any environmental claim must be supported by solid, verifiable evidence. The proposals require that claims be checked by independent and accredited verifiers.

⁸³ European Commission. 2024. Green claims (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/green-claims_en). Accessed: 9.5.2025.

Claims must be clear, specific, and avoid general statements that can be interpreted in multiple ways.

EU Eco-label

The EU Ecolabel is the EU's official voluntary certification for products and services with reduced environmental impact.⁸⁴ It signifies environmental excellence, enhances consumer trust, and ensures compliance with EU regulations. The label provides a competitive edge by appealing to eco-conscious consumers and aligning with sustainability standards.

To apply, businesses must identify the product group, ensure compliance, and pre-register in the EU Ecolabel catalogue (ECAT). They submit documentation, pay fees, and undergo assessment. Approved products can display the label. Fees vary by product and company size, with discounts for SMEs and certified businesses. Additional costs may include testing and renewal fees. The process includes a two-month preliminary check and up to six months for additional submissions.

⁸⁴ European Commission. 2024. EU Ecolabel (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/eu-ecolabel_en). Accessed: 9.5.2025.

4. Sustainability assessment and communication

4.1. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

Life cycle Assessment (LCA) is a method for quantifying a product's environmental impacts throughout its lifecycle— from raw material extraction to manufacturing, use, disposal, or recycling.

There are several reasons why doing LCA is important. Firstly, LCA provides a holistic view of the environment, which helps identify the stages where improvement can have the greatest positive environmental impact. LCA results could assist the decision-making processes regarding product development, material selection and process improvement, etc. In addition, it is increasingly required by regulations and regulatory bodies. Furthermore, sustainability is becoming one of the key identifiers of market performance. Companies with better sustainable management and transparency can gain a competitive advantage.

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has established widely accepted processes for carrying out life cycle assessments (LCAs) in its 14000 series of environmental management standards, namely in ISO 14040⁸⁵ and ISO 14044⁸⁶.

The ISO 14000 family sets standards for many aspects of environmental impact of a company, including the Environmental Management Systems, Environmental Audits, Environmental Labeling and Life Cycle Assessment.

Specifically, ISO 14020-14025 specifies Eco-labels and declarations, namely:

- ISO 14024: Principles & Procedures for Environmental Labeling (Type I)
- ISO 14021 / 14022 / 14023: Self-declared labels (Type II) and
- ISO 14025: Environmental Product Declarations (Type III)

ISO 14040 defines the principles and frameworks to conduct a qualified life Cycle Assessment, including how the LCI (Life Cycle Inventory), and LCIA (Life Cycle Impact Assessment) are conducted. In compensation to the methodology in practice, ISO 14044 specifies the specific requirements and guidelines for correct conduction of an LCA.

In addition, ISO 14067 defines how to quantify the carbon footprint of products during a Life Cycle Assessment.

⁸⁵ ISO 14040:2006. Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework.

⁸⁶ ISO 14044:2006. ... — Requirements and guidelines. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland.

Product lifecycle phases

There are different levels of LCA which cover certain stages during the whole life cycle. For instance, cradle-to-grave LCA covers the entire lifecycle from raw material extraction to disposal, whereas cradle-to-gate focuses only on processes up to manufacturing, as indicated in **Figure 8**.

Figure 85. Lifecycle phases.

There are four commonly used frameworks for LCA according to the needs and availability of data. BSB refers to Beyond System boundaries, which include the recycle, reuse phases if necessary.

Cradle – to – grave

Cradle-to-grave involves all five phases of a product’s lifecycle, from raw materials to the waste disposal and recycling phase. The cradle stands for the product with the sourcing of the raw materials, and the grave stands for the last phase of the lifecycle which is the waste disposal. In other words, cradle-to-grave LCA assesses the environmental footprint of your product’s full life cycle.

Cradle – to – cradle

The Cradle-to-Cradle design framework, also known as also referred to as 2CC2, C2C, cradle 2 cradle, was first established by Michael Braungart and William McDonough⁸⁷. It essentially minimizes the concept of waste by emphasizing the idea of developing things using materials that can be continuously recycled or biodegraded keeping materials in the

⁸⁷ McDonough, W. and Braungart, M., 2002. Cradle to cradle: remaking the way we make things. New York: North Point Press.

economic loop. Since the loop is “closed” using reusable materials, it is often referred to within the concept of Circular Economy.

Compared to cradle – to – grave framework, cradle – to – cradle method is used when the materials are reusable and recycled. Both cradle-to-cradle and cradle-to-grave demonstrate the complete lifecycle of a product, while the lifecycle ends when the product is disposed as a waste, the lifecycle continues if the product is recycled at the end of its life, which leads to the cradle-to-cradle LCA framework.

Cradle – to – gate

Cradle-to-gate is one of the frameworks that assesses the first two phases of the product lifecycle, which is from the raw materials extraction to the manufacturing and processing phase in factories before the product is transported to the retail stage. This framework has a shorter chain which makes the cradle-to-gate more time efficient, and the complexity of analysis is reduced. In addition, acquiring lifecycle information from the use and product disposal phases can be difficult. However, it is worth noting that some standards may require other approaches, for example, EN15804+A2 requires a cradle-to-grave approach.

Gate – to – gate

Gate-to-gate LCA framework focuses solely on one specific phase of a product’s lifecycle, which is commonly used when the whole value chain of the product has high complexity. The analysis of the most value-added process could speed up the assessment process and improve the efficiency of product design at early stages.

Conducting an LCA

Conducting a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) involves a systematic, phased approach to evaluate the environmental impacts of a product, process, or service throughout its entire life cycle. The ISO standardization outlines four main phases in the LCA framework shown in **Figure 9**.

Figure 96. Main steps of LCA.

Goal and scope definition

Establish the objectives of the LCA study, including the intended application, reasons for conducting the assessment, the target audience, and whether the results will be used in comparative assertions intended for public disclosure.

Define the system boundaries, functional unit (a measure of the function of the studied system), assumptions, limitations, and the impact categories to be considered. This phase sets the context and ensures that the assessment aligns with its intended purpose.

Life Cycle Inventory Analysis (LCIA)

Gather comprehensive data on all inputs and outputs associated with the product system. This includes raw material extraction, energy consumption, water usage, emissions to air, water, and soil, and waste generation.

Develop a detailed flow diagram of the processes involved in the product's life cycle to identify and quantify the relevant flows within the system boundaries.

Impact assessment

Based on the inventory data collected in the previous step, the environmental impact in different categories like Global warming (kg CO₂ eq.), Acidification (kg SO₂ eq.), Ozone Depletion (kg CFC-11 eq.), etc., are calculated. Table 1 illustrates the core environmental impact indicators of the Environmental Footprint EF 3.1. method.

Table 1. Environmental impact categories according to EF 3.1⁸⁸.

Environmental impact category	Indicator	Unit	Unit description
Climate change	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	The equivalent amount of carbon dioxide over a 100-year time horizon, including greenhouse gases CH ₄ , N ₂ O, translated into CO ₂ equivalents.
Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11 _{eq}	The ratio of the impact on ozone of a chemical compared to the impact of a similar mass of CFC-11 (a reference chlorofluorocarbon)
Human toxicity, cancer	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh)	CTUh	CTUh represents the estimated increase in human disease cases per unit mass of a substance emitted for cancer.
Human toxicity, non-cancer	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh)	CTUh	CTUh represents the estimated increase in human disease cases per unit mass of a substance emitted for non-cancer.
Particulate matter	Human health effects associated with exposure to PM2.5.	Disease incidences	Number of additional cases of diseases linked to fine particulate matter exposure.
Ionising radiation, human health	Human exposure efficiency relative to U235	kBq U ²³⁵	Kilobecquerels of radioactive decay activity equivalent to uranium-235, the ionizing radiation exposure.
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOC _{eq}	Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds (NMVOCs) equivalents that contribute to smog formation harmful to health.

⁸⁸ European Commission. 2023. JRC Technical Report. Updated characterisation and normalisation factors for the Environmental Footprint 3.1 method. ISSN 1831-9424.

Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol H ⁺ _{eq}	Acidifying emissions measured as moles of hydrogen ion equivalents
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol N _{eq}	Potential for nutrient overload in terrestrial ecosystems, measured in nitrogen equivalents.
Eutrophication, freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P _{eq}	Phosphorus-equivalent emissions that can lead to freshwater algae growth and oxygen depletion.
Eutrophication, marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N _{eq}	Nitrogen-equivalent discharges that promote excessive marine plant growth, leading to dead zones.
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	CTUe	Estimated increase in risk for species due to toxic emissions, across ecosystems.
Land use	Soil quality index	Dimensionless (pt)	A point score representing changes in soil quality or land functionality, a relative indicator.
Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)	m ³ world eq. deprived water	Volume of water consumed, weighted by scarcity to show potential deprivation for other users.
Resource use, minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sb _{eq}	The antimony (Sb) equivalents, measuring the depletion of non-renewable mineral resources
Resource use, fossil	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)	MJ	Energy use from fossil resources, measured in megajoules.

In the Impact Assessment, data collected during the inventory phase, such as the inputs for emissions and resource usage, are translated into environmental impact scores across various categories. This process involves applying specific characterization factors derived from established scientific literature to quantify the potential environmental impacts associated with each flow.

One widely used impact assessment method is ReCiPe2016, which offers a comprehensive framework for evaluating environmental impacts at both midpoint and endpoint levels. ReCiPe2016 includes 18 midpoint impact categories and 3 endpoint categories⁸⁹. Midpoint indicators focus on specific environmental problems, such as climate change or acidification, while endpoint indicators provide a higher level of aggregation, reflecting

⁸⁹ RIVM. 2023. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) & ReCiPe (<https://www.rivm.nl/en/life-cycle-assessment-lca/recipe>). Accessed: 9.5.2025.

impacts on broader areas of protection like human health, ecosystem quality, and resource scarcity, as shown in **Figure 10**.

Figure 107. Midpoint level impact categories and their damage pathways to the endpoint level, adapted from ⁹⁰

Another pertinent method is the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1⁹¹, developed by the European Commission to harmonize the measurement of environmental performance. EF 3.1 focuses on 16 midpoint impact categories, providing a structured approach to assess various environmental impacts.

In practice, the choice between midpoint and endpoint approaches depends on the study's objectives. Midpoint indicators offer detailed insights into specific environmental issues, facilitating targeted improvements, while endpoint indicators provide an overarching view of potential damages, aiding in broader decision-making processes.

Interpretation

The Interpretation phase is the final stage of a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), where the findings from the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) and Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) are analyzed to draw meaningful conclusions and provide actionable recommendations.

This phase involves identifying significant environmental issues, evaluating the completeness, sensitivity, and consistency of the data, and determining the robustness of

⁹⁰ Huijbregts et al. 2017. [ReCiPe2016: a harmonised life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level](#). The international journal of life cycle assessment, 22, pp.138-147.

⁹¹ European Commission – Joint Research Centre. 2023. Environmental Footprint transition phase (<https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/EFtransition.html>). Accessed: 9.5.2025.

the findings. The goal is to ensure that the results align with the defined objectives of the study and to assess the reliability of the outcomes.

During interpretation, practitioners systematically review the data to identify key contributors to environmental impacts, assess the influence of assumptions and methodological choices, and ensure that the study's conclusions are well-supported by the data. This process may involve revisiting earlier phases of the LCA to refine data or methodologies based on insights gained during interpretation. By thoroughly conducting this phase, organizations can develop actionable strategies to minimize their environmental footprint and make informed decisions that enhance sustainability.

4.2. Environmental Product Declaration (EPD)

Defined in ISO 14025, an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) is a standardized document that provides detailed and verified information on the environmental impact of a product throughout its life cycle. The objective of EPD is to enhance the transparency and comparability of sustainability performances between products, thus helping consumers and businesses make informed choices. EPDs use LCA as the fundamental methodology and follow the standards ISO 14040. EPDs quantify environmental variables such as potential for climate change, resource use, and water use.

EPDs are commonly used in many industries, including construction, manufacturing, and retail, as a tool to evaluate the sustainable performance of products.

EPD program operators

An EPD program operator carries out the environmental declaration program. Their tasks include the management of creation, verification, registration, and publication of EPDs in line with ISO 14025, which defines the framework for the Type III EPDs.

Table 2 shows a list of major EPD program Operators in Europe, while most of them have a focus on construction and building industry.

Table 2. List of major EPD program operators in Europe.

Country	Program Operator	Website
Sweden	International EPD System (EPD Int'l AB)	environdec.com
Germany	IBU (Institut Bauen und Umwelt)	ibu-epd.com

France	INIES (via Alliance HQE-GBC)	inies.fr
Italy	EPDItaly	epditaly.it
Norway	EPD Norge	epd-norge.no
Finland	Rakennustieto / RTS EPD	epd.rts.fi
Netherlands	MRPI® (Milieu Relevante Product Informatie)	mrpi.nl
Austria	bau-EPD	bau-epd.at
Hungary	HUGBC EPD Program	hugbc.hu

Product category rules (PCR)

EPDs are created in accordance with Product Category Rules (PCRs). PCRs, as defined in the ISO 14025:2006 standard, are a requirement for the creation of Type III EPDs.

PCRs provide the guidelines, rules and requirements for developing an EPD for specific product categories. It also provides instructions for how the LCA should be conducted. PCRs ensure that functionally similar products are assessed uniformly, allowing for comparable and transparent EPDs. PCRs are usually developed by multiple stakeholders, including program operators, trade organizations, academic experts, researchers or individual companies.

PCRs can be found on the websites of EPD program operators. For example, the International EPD System ⁹² provides a broad, searchable PCR library. For European construction products, operators like IBU, EPDItaly, INIES, and EPD Norge offer PCRs aligned with EN 15804. New PCRs are developed if there are no appropriate PCRs for the product.

EPD process

EPD development follows the steps outlined in **Figure 11**.

⁹² EPD International. 2025. The International EPD® System (<https://www.environdec.com/home>). Accessed: 9.5.2025.

Figure 11. EPD process overview.

Third-party verification and publishing

After the necessary data are collected and generated, LCA results and non-LCA data should be combined into a standardized EPD format. The report structure should be aligned with the selected PCR and ISO 14025 guidelines.

EPD should be verified by an accredited third-party verifier before getting published. Verified EPD will get a unique registration number. Each EPD program operator maintains its own list of approved verifiers. For example, the International EPD system lists its approved individual verifiers and certification bodies on its website. However, if the two programs have a Mutual Recognition Agreement (MRA), it may be possible to use a verifier from one program for publishing in another.

Cost of EPD development

Creating an EPD requires a detailed and multi-step process, with each phase adding to the total expenses involved.

A study by Tasaki et al. ⁹³ provides a detailed analysis of the costs associated with creating Product Category Rules (PCRs) and EPDs. The findings indicate that the total cost for developing both a PCR and an EPD ranges between \$13,000 and \$41,000, with the workload estimated between 22 to 44 person-days. A report by One Click LCA highlights that the average cost of developing an EPD is around \$15,000⁹⁴.

Beyond the development phase, organizations must consider registration and annual fees imposed by EPD Program Operators. For instance, The International EPD® System⁹⁵, as of May 2025, outlines its fee structure as follows:

Table 3. Publication costs at the International EPD System platform.³

Registration Fee per EPD:	Annual Fee (based on organization size):
1st EPD: €1,000	Micro (1-10 employees): €500
2nd to 4th EPDs: €500 each	SME (11-250 employees): €1,000
5th to 99th EPDs: €100 each	MNE (>250 employees): €2,500
100th EPD onwards: €50 each	Industry association: €1,000

Several factors influence the overall cost of EPD development, including the complexity of the product, as intricate supply chains or manufacturing processes often require more detailed LCAs, increasing both time and financial investment; data availability, as the ease of accessing accurate and comprehensive data significantly impacts the workload and cost; geographical considerations, such as regional differences in labour rates and the availability of qualified professionals; and program operator fees, as varying fee structures among EPD Program Operators can affect the total expenditure.

⁹³ Tasaki, T., Shobatake, K., Nakajima, K. and Dalhammar, C., 2017. [International survey of the costs of assessment for environmental product declarations](#). *Procedia CIRP*, 61, pp.727-731.

⁹⁴ One Click LCA. 2023. [The Business Case for Investing in EPDs](#). Accessed: 9.5.2025.

⁹⁵ EPD International. 2024. [Pricing for 2025](#). Accessed: 9.5.2025.